

Sample Name: PA <1 μm

Material: Polyamide (Nylon-6,6)

Size: <1 μm

Production Partner: Wessling

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Structure

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- 75% particles are <1 μm
- Particles have a rounded, irregular morphology
- 2.0×10^{11} particles per gram
- 11200 cm²/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- S, Na, Si, P, Cu and Rb contaminants detected by ICP-MS
 - Na, Si, P, Cu and Rb ≤1 μg/g
- No changes due to milling observed in Raman spectrum
- Cathodoluminescence shows typical PA spectrum with no evidence of degradation, lower intensity is due to particle size

Description of terms

- D[4,3]: Volume mean (μm)
- D[3,2]: Surface area mean (μm)
- D[2,1]: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- D[1,0]: Number length mean (μm)
- D50_v: Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D50_N: Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w: Number of particles per gram plastic (#/g)
- A_w: Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm²/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using *Static Light Scattering (SLS)* provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
7.38	3.89	1.81	0.99	0.68	5.60	2.0×10^{11}	11200

Morphology (using *Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)* provided by TNO)

Chemical Composition (using ICP-MS provided by Wessling)

Element	Concentration
S	25 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Na	1 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Si	1 $\mu\text{g/g}$
P	1 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Rb	<1 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Cu	<1 $\mu\text{g/g}$

Raman Spectroscopy (provided by Wessling)